

AN INNOVATIVE INTERPRETATION OF THE LEVEL OF CRIMINALITY OF FOREIGNERS LEGALLY PRESENT IN ITALY

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ABSTRACT: An Innovative Interpretation of the Level of Criminality of Foreigners Legally Present in Italy.

The article aims to explore two considerations: the heightened concern among Italians regarding crime and the tendency to believe the proportion of crimes they commit is abnormal compared to their incidence among the resident population. The paper refers to some studies conducted with Franco Pittau, which were included in the annual reports of the IDOS Study and Research Center on immigrant deviance and at the International Interdisciplinary Conference On Immigration. The inspiring reasons for the studies on immigrant crime were fundamentally two: one social (Italians' fear) and the other methodological (the failure to take into account all the statistical data essential for a correct assessment). The paper will present the evolution of the debate on criminality among regular immigrants from the 1990s to the present, a period in which Italy became a country of mass immigration. This study does not entirely agree with the conclusions of two well-known sociologists of those decades in that they believe that regularly resident immigrants are involved, proportionally, in a much higher number of reports compared to their impact on the resident population. With a different statistical methodology, also evaluating not unknown elements and adding others, we can free the legal immigrant from this criminal connotation, through an approach capable of promoting greater openness among Italians on the issue. of integration.

Summary: 1. Proposal Of An Interpretative Line; 2.The Alarm Aroused By The Phenomenon Of Crime; 3.The Statistical Archives On Crime In Italy; 4.The Historical Trend Of Crime By Foreigners; 5. A Different Interpretation Of Crime By Regularly Resident Immigrant 6.Recalculation Of Complaints Against Resident Aliens; 7.Crime Referred To Foreigners Irregularly Or Unstably Present In Italy; 7.1 The Crime Rate Calculated By Eurostat 7.2

The presence of foreign citizens in prisons; 7.3 Distorting factors: pre-trial detention and alternative measures to detention; 7.4 Violations of the TUI; 7.5 Summary of results 8. Conclusions.

Keywords: *Foreign crime, complaints, Italy, interpretation of data, Istat, Ministry of the Interior, Ministry of Justice*

1. Proposed line of interpretation

This article takes particular account of the widespread sense of security among Italians in the face of crime, while it does not agree with the thesis, prevalent among academics, that there is an abnormal exposure of immigrants to deviance: this argument is not considered statistically well-founded with regard to foreign citizens legally present in the country¹.

In preparing this contribution, the following scholarly opinions were taken into account what has been explained by the scholars Marzio Barbagli and Luigi Solivetti, whose interpretation is disputed for the arguments we will see. Barbagli dealt with the issue ² in the first decade of the 2000s ³.

1 This contribution recalls the paper presented at the International Interdisciplinary Conference on Immigration: 'Sguardi incrociati' promoted by the University of Sfax and the Tunisian Association of Mediterranean Studies at the University of Sousse, 17-19 December 2018. The article recalls the studies conducted with Franco Pittau (founder and creator of the Dossier Statistico Immigrazione and Editor-in-Chief of the journal *Affari Sociali Internazionali*: until 2015 he was President of the IDOS Study and Research Centre) over the last five years and the chapters on immigrant deviance in the annual reports of the IDOS Study and Research Centre, Dossier Statistico Immigrazione and Osservatorio Romano sull'immigrazione and continued over the years by the Idos Study and Research Centre.

2 Studies on the criminality of immigrants, which began in Europe after the Second World War in conjunction with the large influx of immigrants, have had Germany as their main outlet See for more details: H.G. Zimmermann 'Die Kriminalität der ausländischen Arbeiter', in *Kriminalistik*, 1996, pp.623-635). Something similar would also have happened in Belgium, for which these authors were cited: Liben G., «Un réffet de la criminalité italienne dans la region de Liège », in *Reveu de Droit Pénal et de Criminologie* 44, 1963, pp.205-246; Debuyst C., «Notes sur la délinquance des étrangers », in *Annales de Droit* 4, 1970, pp.557-568. Giuliana Urso, 2010, *Immigrazione e criminalità: teorie e dati*, LUISS Internal Paper, Rome.

3 M. Barbagli, *Immigrazione e criminalità in Italia*, 1998, Il Mulino, Bologna; M Barbagli. 2011,- A Colombo edited by *Rapporto sulla Criminalità e sicurezza in Italia - 2010*, Ministero dell'Interno, Fondazione ICSA, Gruppo 24 ore.

Luigi M. Solivetti wrote predominantly in the second decade and his last considered essay was published at the Hume Foundation website.⁴ Their conclusions, at the end of treatises that are in many respects appreciable, cannot be shared for statistical reasons, since in their essays, data are overlooked, which are available and to be valued because they are capable of modifying the judgement on the foreign component.

This is the approach of the article: in view of the growing concern of citizens about the phenomenon of crime, an overview is needed to avoid unfounded conclusions, an analysis of the specific statistical archives available in Italy, an overview of the trend of the crime phenomenon, a presentation of a different criterion for interpreting crimes concerning resident foreign immigrants, as well as an analysis of the case of non-resident foreigners. It should be noted that the interpretation proposed here, with reference to offences committed by legally resident foreign nationals, does not apply to those who are illegally resident. The rigorous use of crime statistics, as set out in this paper (and also in the authors cited, who, however, did not give weight to certain statistical factors), makes it possible to counteract the process of criminalisation of the migration phenomenon (not in the authors cited, but in the collective imagination), which tends to become more and more of a mass prejudice.

The thesis I am presenting recalls the studies of the IDOS Study and Research Centre, which publishes the Statistical Dossier on Immigration (now in its 34 st annual edition in 2024) and which since its earliest years has collected all available data on the migration phenomenon, including those on crime, moving over time from their presentation to their interpretation. Franco Pittau, until a few years ago president of the centre and editor of the articles on crime, who has been involved in its research for several years and whose itinerary I am now continuing, has distinguished himself in this endeavour.⁵

4 L. M. Solivetti, *Crimine e Immigrazione in Italia*, Roma, 2018, in <http://www.fondazionehume.it/societa/crimine-e-immigrazione-in-italia/#more-11452>, among other works, see, for example, L. M. Solivetti, *Immigrazione, società e crimine. Dati e considerazioni sul caso Italia*. Edizioni Il Mulino, Bologna, 2013. Previously, in addition to theses on this subject published abroad, he edited the book *Il Mulino, nel 2004, il volume Immigrazione, integrazione e crimine*. <https://www.fondazionehume.it/author/luigi-solivetti/>, L.M Solivetti, 2010. *Immigration, Social Integration and Crime: A Cross-National Approach*. Abingdon – New York: Routledge.

5 See, e.g., *Dossier*, 2014, pp. 183-189; *Dossier* 2015, pp. 175-178; *Dossier* 2017, pp. 181-185; *Dossier* 2018, pp. 185-190; *Osservatorio* 2016, pp. 106-111; *Osservatorio* 2017, pp. 988-106; Coauthors with Luca Di Sciuolo, p.181-190;

The analysis, here conducted on immigrant crime, should then be referred to individual communities and in particular to the largest ones (12 national groups exceed 100,000), but this is beyond the scope of this paper. The monographs conducted by the Idos Study and Research Centre on the communities (previously considered 'rogue communities') have shown the mixture of criminal aspects and regulation of flows in a context of fluidifying arrivals.⁶

This contribution does not go into the merits of crimes, for which the incidence of immigrants is very high, since this is a very serious problem to be tackled not only with the punishments to be imposed on deviants but especially with a work of prevention. The main interest of this study concerns the overall number of complaints, to then make an overall comparison between the deviance of Italians and that of foreigners, as a preparatory basis for more detailed comparisons.

2. The alarm raised by the phenomenon of crime

In addition to being inherently inclined to mistrust foreigners, especially in times of crisis and most recently following the large flows recorded in the Mediterranean in 2014-2017, public opinion is often influenced by inaccurate and even misleading information. The National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT) periodically monitors citizens' fear of crime. In 2015-2016, 27.6 per cent felt little or not at all safe going out alone at night, for 38.2 per cent fear of crime influences their habits a great deal or a fair amount, and, understandably, the sense of insecurity among women and the elderly is much greater. 41.9 per cent of citizens are worried about being robbed or pick-pocketed, 37 per cent about having their car stolen and 28.7 per cent are afraid for themselves or their family members of being sexually assaulted. 60.2% are (very or fairly) worried about house burglaries (the only stable figure). The perception of the risk of crime has an incisive influence (more

6 IDOS, a cura di R. Devole, F. Pittau, A. Ricci, G. Urso, *Gli albanesi in Italia. Conseguenze economiche e sociali dell'immigrazione*, 2008 Edizioni IDOS, Roma, pp. 45-61; Caritas Italiana, a cura di F. Pittau, A. Ricci, A. Silj, 2008, *Romania. Immigrazioni e lavoro in Italia. Statistiche, problemi e prospettive*, Edizioni Idos, giugno pp. 137-149; IDOS, edited by Ginevra Demaio e Franco Pittau, 2013. *La comunità marocchina in Italia. Un ponte sul Mediterraneo/La Communauté marocaine en Italie. Un pont sur la Méditerranée*, Edizioni IDOS, Roma.

than in the past) on the sense of bewilderment and unease that citizens feel. Similarly, the opinion on the control of the territory by the police is negative, more than in the past, for 46.4% of individuals.⁷

Various studies have shown that in the media, the term 'immigration' is predominantly associated with crime news. People are concerned because they consider immigrants to be a threat to their personal safety and their property regardless of their behaviour, just because of their mere presence: that is, they consider them to be naturally predisposed to crime, believing the thesis continually repeated by politicians and the media. This is a complex phenomenon of social psychology, which today concerns the attitude of the Italian population towards immigrants, whereas in the past it concerned the behaviour of the population of the countries that welcomed Italian emigrants. Particular care must be taken to avoid these fearful reactions, and consequent closure, in contexts where the immigrant presence is more substantial. Mass media operators can also accentuate the negative reactions of the population. According to the Romanian journalist Miruna Cajvaneanu, 'journalists, especially TV journalists, are also partly to blame, because the TV of fear' makes share'.⁸

Very critical of the information was the Charter of Rome Association, which approved a document containing indications on how to correctly report on immigrants and asylum seekers, going beyond mere emergency reporting.⁹ What is of most interest here is the distorted perception of the relationship between immigration and crime, which is attributable to those who, starting from concrete facts and real problems, do not refrain from unfounded generalisations. In addition, this aspect has contributed to accrediting the image of immigrants as being more likely to commit crimes, thus supporting mistrust towards them. One applies to an entire group what one refers to the individual, one does not distinguish between the resident immigrant (for whom Italy is his new country where he intends to lead his life) and the multitude of other foreigners who may or may not be in Italy temporarily, regularly or not, just as one also fails to distinguish between common crime and organised crime, between crimes that concern both Italians and foreigners and

7 ISTAT, La percezione del crimine, in <https://www.istat.it/it/files/2018/06/Report-Percezione-della-sicurezza.pdf>

8 Romanian journalist, in 'Roma Today', 23 February 2015.

9 www.cartadiroma.org.

those that concern only foreigners (relating to non-compliance with the rules on entry and residence in Italy).¹⁰

3. Statistical archives on crime in Italy

The archives of the Ministry of the Interior.

This file, set up by Law No. 21 of 1981 (Art. 9), includes complaints submitted to the police (prosecution on the basis of a complaint by a party) and in some cases made *ex officio* (prosecution *ex officio*) by the police or by the judicial authorities (arrest in the act of committing a crime, as well as in cases of criminal conspiracy, resistance to a public official, drug trafficking, cases in which the individual victim and the complaint by a party are missing). It is now well known that the reports made by the victims are only a part of the crimes they suffer: non-complaints are linked to psychological, social and family qualms (among both Italians and foreigners). This file, although managed inter-force, is structured at the Ministry of the Interior/Central Directorate of Criminal Police. The methodology for collecting complaints was revised in 2004, the year in which the other law enforcement agencies were added to the public security corps and the Carabinieri and, in addition, the types of offences were expanded. Therefore, for reasons of statistical homogeneity, detailed comparisons with the years before 2004 are not recommended.

In this file, called the 'Investigation System/SDI', complaints concerning both Italian and foreign citizens (no matter whether resident or non-resident) suspected of having committed a crime are recorded separately. The complaints registered in this archive do not take into account whether they have had a judicial follow-up, a requirement that characterises the complaints collected in the archive of the Ministry of Justice (which are only about 60% of the cases registered by the Ministry of the Interior). These are broken down by provinces, by main offences and different communities, as far as foreign nationals are concerned, whereas usually only reports concerning certain criminal offences are provided to researchers.

The data, which the SDI archive makes available, are broken down by the types of crime considered most significant for security purposes: bombings, massacres, voluntary consummated homicides, attempted

10 On organised crime, including foreign crime, the Anti-Mafia Investigative Directorate (DIA) publishes a biannual report for Parliament, which can be consulted on the website direzioneeinvestigativaantimafia.interno.gov.it

homicides, manslaughter, malicious wounding, battery, threats, insults, sexual violence, sexual acts with minors, corruption of minors, theft, receiving stolen goods, robberies, kidnappings, criminal conspiracy, money laundering and use of money, fraud and computer fraud, fire damage, smuggling, drugs, exploitation of prostitution and child pornography. Other types of offences, such as violations of entry and residence regulations, although significant in number, are not made available separately to researchers.

The Ministry of Justice Archives

These are the complaints that have had a judicial follow-up, reported by the Public Prosecutors' Offices and collected in the Ministry of Justice archive, to be further processed by the National Institute of Statistics. The data collected are broken down by type of crime, persons reported, territories involved and persons definitively sentenced. These data are available from Istat (from the year 1998 onwards) and allow the historical reconstruction of deviance in Italy in the most recent period, as indeed Solivetti has done.

In this archive, the reported persons are distinguished between those born in Italy (among whom there is also a quota of foreign citizens) and those born abroad (among whom there is a quota of repatriated Italian citizens and foreign citizens who have acquired Italian citizenship), so that the number of reported foreigners is not immediately available but only obtainable by approximation at the end of certain corrective operations (unlike in the Ministry of the Interior's archive).

The incidence of women in this archive is just under one-fifth of the total (this is also the case in the Ministry of the Interior's archive) despite the fact that women far outnumber men among resident foreign immigrants (while on average they only outnumber men by a few percentage points). The problem of foreign crime especially concerns first-generation adults. The behaviour of the second generation¹¹ in particular by forming gangs, participating in fights and other manifestations of deviance, has been visible for some years now but still constitutes a modest share within foreign crime¹².

11 D. Melossi, Dario, A. De Giorgi e E. Massa 2008. "Minori stranieri tra conflitto normativo e devianza: la seconda generazione si confessa?" *Sociologia del Diritto* (2): 99–130.

12 F. Pittau, 2010, "Riflessioni sul fenomeno della criminalità tra gli immigrati in Italia alla luce di alcune recenti studi", in *Rassegna italiana di criminologia* (numeri 3-4

The principle of circularity of sources

The approach proposed in this article is holistic and starts from an overview in order to then address the particular aspects of the crime. Reference to all available sources is indispensable because each of them, although partial, contains original cognitive elements and failure to take them into account can lead to disputable interpretations.

The two main sources are, as previously seen, the Archives of the Ministry of the Interior and the Archives of the Ministry of Justice, which are however not sufficient to safeguard the principle of circularity of sources. For their correct interpretation it is indispensable to also know the archive on residence permits issued to non-EU citizens, the archive on foreign residents, the estimate of irregularly present immigrants, the breakdown of complaints regarding foreigners' violations of the Consolidated Immigration Act (obtainable from the Ministry of the Interior Archive, but for many years neither publicised nor provided to researchers), the estimate of people who in a certain year enter from abroad to stay in Italy for at least one night.

If one neglects the use of all these sources, relying only on ministerial files of complaints and charges, one comes to conclusions that do not fully reflect reality. This is the case when an abnormal exposure to crime of legally resident immigrants (compared to their incidence on the total resident population) is proposed as a clear and indisputable conclusion.

4. Historical crime trends of foreigners

Reconstruction of the historical series of complaints 2004-2017 recorded by the Ministry of the Interior¹³.

In Italy, the strong increase in resident crime that started in the 1970s continued in the 1980s and was consolidated in the early 1990s. For instance, homicides consumed, which rose sharply in the 1960s until they peaked in 1991, experienced the lowest rate in the historical series in 2006.

del 1999: 501-520; Idem, "Immigrati e criminalità. Cosa dicono i dati", in *Etnografia e ricerca qualitativa*, 1/2010: 119-125; U. Melotti, 2011, *Migrazioni e sicurezza. Criminalità, conflitti urbani, terrorismo*. Chieti: Solfanelli.

13 The statistical data considered here were provided by the Central Criminal Police Directorate of the Ministry of the Interior and published in the various editions of the *Dossier Statistico Immigrazione*.

The involvement of immigrants in the crime scenario started in the 1970s, a period in which Italy, while continuing to be a country of emigration, also began to become an outlet for foreign nationals, who had fled their countries of origin under the pressure of powerful expulsion factors and were rejected by other European states following the restrictive policies adopted after the 1973 oil crisis. The incidence of foreigners (including legal immigrants and other categories of foreigners present on Italian territory), calculated on the total number of complaints with a known author, hovered between 4% and 9% until 1996, then exceeded 10% and reached 19% between 1997 and 2000.

Over time, the immigrant presence has not only become more substantial, but has also been characterised by a tendency towards family and long-term settlement, while in terms of deviance, organised crime has been joined by common delinquency. In the new century, migratory pressure continued and, in addition to planned entry flows, four regularisations were launched (2002¹⁴, 2009¹⁵, 2012¹⁶ e 2020¹⁷). The entry quotas then decreased until they were almost eliminated after the 2012 regularisation, with the exception of seasonal workers and the conversion of residence permits for some categories already in Italy.

During this period, the number of complaints increased but not in direct proportion to the increase in foreign presence, so one cannot speak of a direct causal relationship between immigration and crime.

In the first decade of the century, the incidence of complaints against foreigners was high and peaked in 2007 (35.2%). From 2010 onwards, the increase in the number of complaints was continuous until 2014, when 304,942 complaints against foreigners were registered, before decreasing in 2015 and 2016, the year with the lowest number of complaints since 2006 (261,269 complaints). In the period 2004-2016, complaints against foreigners increased by a total of 13.9 per cent against an increase in resident immigrants of 128.3 per cent. Taking these numbers into account, one cannot speak of a 'catastrophic' trend in foreign crime, which has improved in terms of the number of complaints (naturally in relation to the aforemen-

14 Decree-Law No 195 of 9 September 2002, converted with amendments into Law No 222 of 9 October 2002.

15 Decree-Law No. 78 of 1 July 2009, converted into Law No. 102 of 3 August 2009

16 Legislative Decree No. 109 of 16 July 2012

17 Art.103 Decree-Law No. 34 19/05/2020 converted by L. 17.07.2020 No. 77.

tioned increase in the resident foreign population) and their incidence on the total, although there are still some problematic aspects, especially for certain criminal offences.

In 2017, the total number of complaints against known perpetrators was 911,836, of which 634,400 related to resident Italian citizens and 277,436 to foreign citizens (whether legally resident or not, i.e. both irregular and transient). Complaints against non-residents and irregulars totalled 67.8% of the 277,436 complaints filed against foreigners in 2018. Between 2016 and 2017 (a year deeply marked by the crisis of the flows in the Mediterranean), complaints against foreigners (resident or not) increased by 6.2% (from 261,269 to 277,436), with the incidence on the total of complaints with known perpetrators rising from 29.2% to 30.4%. In contrast, complaints against Italians decreased from 732,438 to 634,400 (-13.4%). However, over the long term, 2007-2017, complaints decreased for foreigners (-0.5%) and increased for Italians (+20.7%): the initial values in 2007 were 301,408 (for foreigners) and 557,861 complaints (for Italians) respectively.

The percentage incidence of complaints on women is similar: 16.4% for foreigners and 17.4% for Italians. However, Italian women have an almost uniform incidence on the total number of complaints for all age groups (between 15% and 18%). For foreign women, on the other hand, the percentage incidence is highest in the age group up to 13 years (18.2%, then decreasing to 13%), then exceeding 22% from the age of 45 and even reaching 32% from the age of 65.

A development to be considered positive overall

Between 2004 and 2016, the Italian resident population decreased by 0.2% and complaints against Italians increased by 31.7%. In contrast, during the same period, the resident immigrant population more than doubled with a significantly more satisfactory trend in complaints (the increase was 2.5 times smaller).¹⁸

In the period taken into consideration, 2006 is a particularly significant year, since it was placed at the end of a five-year period of strong migratory influxes, which were partly reduced in the subsequent long period of crisis (in any case marked by two regularisations, one in 2009 and

18 It is also significant to point out that the increase in complaints against foreigners is half that of the total complaints lodged against Italians and foreigners (+25.8%).

the other in 2012). Among other things, 2006 is also the year in which the highest number of residence permits for work reasons was registered (520,000), a level surpassed only in the 2002 regularisation when more than 700,000 applications were submitted.

It was feared that the global crisis, which has had negative consequences especially on immigrants and in Italy, would have a negative impact on foreign crime trends, but this was not the case. This meteoric rise has not translated into a proportional increase in complaints against foreigners because, as several studies have shown, there is no direct causal relationship between immigration and crime.

Differentiated trend depending on the type of crime

The trend of complaints against foreigners cannot only be read in a negative light.

In general, it is found that foreigners are more involved in various instrumental crimes (thefts and robberies, for example) and also in crimes resulting from impulsive actions, such as fights, malicious injuries, sexual violence, attempted and consummated murders.

The period from 2004 to 2016 shows, with reference to the values recorded in these two years, improvements, deteriorations and stable situations.

Improvements. The percentage incidence of complaints against foreigners (out of the total number of complaints filed) decreased in 2016 for several types of offences (the percentages of complaints against foreigners out of the total number of complaints concerning each type of offence are given in brackets) Mafia-type associations (3.0%), criminal conspiracy (22.2%), smuggling (30.6%), computer crimes (21.43%), theft (42.7%), insults (12.2), voluntary consummated murder (19.9%), manslaughter (10.2%, a reduction of two thirds), manslaughter (10.6%), money laundering (20.6%), computer fraud (11.5%, a value halved in 2016 compared to 2004), usury (4.4%), infringement of intellectual property (27.1%, a value also halved). It is noted, however, that, in many cases, the incidences, although decreased in 2016, are still very high.

Stable situation. This situation (including increases around 1%) concerns the following offences: attacks (16.4 % complaints against foreigners compared to total complaints), sexual acts with minors (18.8%), fire damage (16.4%); extortion (19.2%), threats (17.7%), kidnapping (40.2%), non-compliance with the law on drugs (36.2%).

Increase in incidence. The upward variation (recorded in 2016 compared to 2004) concerns several offences: with an increase of five percentage points counterfeiting of trademarks (52.2% complaints against foreigners compared to the total complaints for this crime), with an increase of about three percentage points corruption of minors (16.8%), with an increase of three percentage points damage (27.9%), with an increase of four and a half points arson (19.0%), with an increase of about three points malicious injury (29.0%), with an increase of two points battery (22,4%), an increase of two and a half points in robberies (36.5%), an increase of two and a half points in receiving stolen goods (42.7%), an increase of six and a half points in the exploitation of prostitution and pornography (55.0%), an increase of five points in massacres (50.0%, although there were only 12 cases), an increase of about two and a half points in attempted murders (32.7%) and an increase of four points in sexual violence (38.2%). The three cases of infanticide recorded in 2016 involved only foreigners. In particular, in 2018, the highest incidence of foreigners is found among the reports/arrests for exploitation of prostitution and child pornography (58.2%), including through the dissemination of audio-visual material downloaded from the web, and counterfeiting of trademarks and industrial products (57.2%), i.e. for selling counterfeit goods. In addition, there are also offences of infringement of intellectual property (31.3%), such as the duplication and sale of copyrighted music tracks, and receiving stolen goods (44.2%) related to these activities.

A significant proportion of complaints/arrests against foreigners is also found for offences typical of so-called petty crime, such as theft (44.2%), robbery (41.1%) and drug trafficking (40.7%), to which are linked - with percentages of involvement in line with the overall average for foreigners - malicious injuries (32,7%) and bodily harm (29.8%), worrying instead are the incidences that the latter have in complaints/arrests for sexual violence (41.8%) and kidnapping (38.5%), types of crimes of higher social alarm.

Reflecting on these figures, which present both lights and shadows, one must always bear in mind that the heading, 'foreigners' does not only include resident immigrants, which have more than doubled in the meantime. A criterion to be taken as a basis for assessing the trend is the incidence of complaints against foreigners out of the total number of complaints lodged (27.6%), which amounts to approximately 226,000 (the remaining just over 53,000 being complaints/arrests of persons

of unknown nationality): beyond this threshold, the situation must be considered even more problematic. It does not matter whether these are instrumental offences to obtain means of subsistence or expressions of personal violence against third parties. Moreover, it should not be overlooked that several cases in which foreigners are heavily involved exert a strong negative impression on public opinion.

5. A different reading of crime among legally resident immigrants

After an initial consideration of the data on complaints against foreigners, one is struck by their overexposure, on which attention is understandably focused.

Based on the Ministry of the Interior's archive, comparing the complaints registered in 2016 to the two population groups (Italian and foreign), the percentage values are very different: 1.13 complaints for every 100 Italians and 5.1 for every 100 foreigners.

In order to define whether this is the 'actual truth' also with regard to foreigners legally resident in Italy, it is necessary to introduce new elements of evaluation.

First element of assessment. It is crucial to bear in mind that only a part of the complaints against foreigners is attributed to legally resident immigrants. In the past, the Central Directorate of the Criminal Police at the Ministry of the Interior, where the complaints archive is maintained, cross-referenced the data on complaints with those on legal residents and distinguished the different criminal burden owed to them compared to irregularly present or, in any case, transient immigrants. In 2005, legally resident foreigners were involved in complaints against foreigners in only 28.9 per cent of cases.

This breakdown of the total number of complaints is not reported either in the reports on security or in the report on foreigners in Italy, both published by the Ministry of the Interior in 2007¹⁹, which limited themselves to providing indications, for various criminal offences, between Italians and foreigners (without distinguishing between them), whereas a continuous and precise update would have been highly desirable.

19 Rapporto sulla criminalità in Italia: Analisi, Prevenzione, Contrasto – Ministero dell'interno, 2007, https://www1.interno.gov.it/mininterno/export/sites/default/it/assets/files/14/0900_rapporto_criminalita.pdf

Although the figure was subsequently neither published by the Ministry of Interior nor provided to researchers, the unequal distribution of reports between irregular immigrants and all other present and non-resident foreigners, on the one hand, and legally resident immigrants on the other, continues to exist. Probably taking into account the increasing flows in recent years and the consequent increase in irregularity, as well as the increase in temporary presences, it is reasonable to assume that the share of complaints attributable to legally resident foreigners could be between 25% and 30%.²⁰

Second element of assessment. It is then necessary to identify the offences that can be attributed exclusively to foreign citizens: these are those that are configured as violations of the Consolidated Immigration Act (approved by Legislative Decree No. 286 of 1998), to be considered distinct from offences of resistance to public officials, which also concern Italians. This group of offences should not be counted when comparing the criminality of foreigners and that of Italians in order to establish their respective differential rates, since the latter are not subject to the criminal offences of illegal entry and stay.

Among the approximately 3,000 types of offences in which the Ministry of the Interior's archive is structured, there are as many as 18 complaints concerning violations of the Consolidated Immigration Act and they concern, for example, irregular entry, expiry or revocation of residence permits or visas, expulsions (Articles 13 and 14 of the Consolidated Immigration Act and Article 10 bis), cases that clearly concern only foreigners.

The number of these complaints should always be disaggregated because they cannot be attributed to legally resident foreigners. This was done in the 2012 ISTAT Report, which, on the basis of the complaints registered in 2009 by the Ministry of the Interior, quantified their incidence as 17.7% of the total number of complaints for that year.

If the share of complaints pertaining to legally resident immigrants were still the same as in 2005 or 2007 (around 30% of the total number

20 It must be borne in mind that the Ministry of the Interior is always able to implement this distinction by cross-referencing the complaints with non-EU residents. Community immigrants, on the other hand, since 2007, in application of a European directive, are no longer subject to the request for a residence permit: in order to extend the distinction between residents and non-EU residents to them as well, the complaints archive should be cross-referenced with the residents archive managed by ISTAT.

of complaints) and the share of violations of the Immigration Consolidation Act was the same as that published by ISTAT in 2012 (around 18% of complaints), the crime rate of foreigners would be similar to that of Italians and probably even slightly lower.

Third element of evaluation. It remains to be added that even the number of officially registered regular presences is lower than the actual regular presence, because there are residence permit holders and EU citizens (recently arrived within the framework of free movement within the EU) who have not yet registered in the register of residents. The Dossier Statistico Immigrazione monitors this situation annually and it has risen from a high of over 500,000 regulars not yet registered in the recent past to about 300,000 in 2017²¹.

6. Recalculation of complaints against resident aliens

Complaints against resident immigrants (5,255,503, or 8.7 per cent of the Italian population, an increase of 6.8 per cent from 2013 to 2018) in 2017 need to be restated, contemplating not the total number of complaints, but those that actually concern them and breaking them down by age group. As mentioned earlier, 2005 was the last time that the Dossier Statistico Immigrazione was informed of the share of complaints concerning immigrants legally settled in Italy: in that year it was 28.9 per cent of the total number of complaints.

In 2017, according to the new communication from the SDI archive authority, the share of complaints against resident immigrants was 32.5 per cent: as to be expected, the increase was undoubtedly influenced by the doubling of the resident foreign population over more than a decade. Thus, of the 277,436 complaints against foreigners, only 90,167 concern resident immigrants, while the remaining two-thirds (187,250) concern other foreigners, either in transit or staying in Italy illegally. After making this breakdown, the complaint rate is 1.50 per cent for Italians (as will be seen later) and 1.75 per cent for resident immigrants: a difference that does not equate to an abnormal overexposure to crime, as has often been written, especially since this is not the only mitigating factor. In fact, if one takes into account that among the foreigners, who

21 See "La presenza straniera regolare complessiva nel 2017", in IDOS e Confronti, Dossier Statistico Immigrazione 2018, Edizioni Idos, Roma, 2018, p 112.

had legally settled in Italy in 2017, there were also about 200,000 people who had not yet been registered at the civil registry office, the rate of immigrant complaints decreases by one decimal place.

We consider the same reasoning to be valid, as these arguments are also structural in the data on foreign crime of 2018²². Finally, it is necessary to deduct the complaints concerning the various violations of the rules on the entry and residence of foreigners, which ISTAT in its annual report of 2012 quantified as approximately one-sixth of the total complaints against foreign citizens (and in the meantime their incidence may even have increased).²³ For the sake of completeness, it should be noted that in 2021, administrative deportation orders were executed against 22 subjects discharged from the penitentiaries at the end of their sentences for whom a radicalisation process had been detected²⁴.

At the end of this operation, the reporting rate of legal immigrants becomes slightly lower than that of Italians. This distinction is in no way intended to minimise, let alone incentivise, non-compliance with the rules of the Consolidated Immigration Act, but only to emphasise that foreigners, compared to Italians, are subject to a greater number of prohibitions, a factor that should be neutralised in a comparison of the two populations on an equal footing.

22 L. Di Sciuillo, *Stranieri e criminalità. Analisi storica di un fenomeno strumentalmente distorto* in Dossier Statistico Immigrazione 2021, p.240-243; L. Di Sciuillo "Stranieri? Criminali", *Il principe dei pregiudizi per una facile demonizzazione* in Dossier Statistico Immigrazione 2020, p.240-244; F. Pittau, L. Di Sciuillo, P. Iafrate, 2019, "La criminalità degli stranieri e degli italiani: linee per un corretto confronto", in IDOS-Confronti, Dossier Statistico Immigrazione 2019, IDOS, Roma, p. 200 e segg., The incidence of cases referred to foreigners among the total number of complaints/arrests (including those against unknown persons) is 26.0%, three times higher than that of foreigners in general, among all Italian residents (8.5% in the same year), their 'propensity to delinquency' would be proportionally higher than that of Italians. As previously stated, deviance among irregular foreign citizens is higher because of their status, they cannot access many essential services (including those of assistance and support both to regular work; the available data of the Dossier Statistico Immigrazione 2021 show that the total number of complaints/arrests in 2020 is decreasing compared to 2015, which amounted to 981,000 cases registered in 2013).

23 This is the 2012 Istat Report, which, based on the complaints recorded in 2009 by the Ministry of the Interior, quantified the incidence as 17.7% of the total complaints for that year.

24 *Relazione del Ministero sull'amministrazione della giustizia anno 2021*, p.903, https://www.giustizia.it/cmsresources/cms/documents/anno_giudiziario2022_relazione_amministrazione2021.pdf

Fourth evaluation element

Crime differentials can also be calculated by age group, referring to the resident Italian population and legally resident foreigners.

This requires some preliminary steps. The age groups of Italians have to be reparametrised using the same percentages found among resident immigrants, who are known to be younger. To the new reparametrised numbers, the actual rates of complaints previously recorded must be applied, thus obtaining the number of complaints that would have concerned Italians had they been in the same age group as resident immigrants.

This leads to an increase in the younger population among Italians and, consequently, also to an increase in the number of complaints, which rise from 634,400 to 832,669: the difference is 198,269 additional, i.e. one third more. Based on this new parameter, the percentage rate of complaints by Italians is on average 1.50% (and not 1.14) compared to 11.75% for resident foreigners (gross of complaints concerning the Consolidated Immigration Act, which should not be taken into account in this comparison)²⁵. It should be added that the comparison of crime rates between Italians and resident foreigners must take into account that the 18-49 age group is the one with the highest rate of deviance, in which the percentage concentration of foreigners is considerable.

25 Cf. P. Curzio, 2021, Report on the Administration of Justice in the Year 2020, Supreme Court of Cassation, p.41. For the sake of completeness, it should be noted that the Administration of Justice Report 2020 also shows a decrease in the prisoner figure compared to previous years. In fact, at the end of the year 2020, the prison population (53,364 inmates) compared to 61,174 (inmates at the end of 30 December 2019). Due to the pandemic, alternative measures to detention have increased. In previous years, the proportion of foreign inmates, who account for about one third of the entire prison population, has remained constant (17,344 out of 53,364 as of 31 December 2020), while the ratio has decreased significantly with regard to the application of alternative measures, basically due to social inclusion problems. The majority of foreign detainees as of 31 March 2022 were definitive (11,641), while there were 5,403 defendants and 60 internees. Among the non-finalists, 2,902 were awaiting first trial, 1,245 appellants and 1,077 claimants, Cf. XVIII report on detention conditions of foreigners, See XVIII rapporto sulle condizioni di detenzione di stranieri, <https://www.rapportoantigone.it/diciottesimo-rapporto-sulle-condizioni-di-detenzione/stranieri-detenuti/#:~:text=I%20detenuti%20stranieri%20al%2031,1.245%20appellanti%20e%201.077%20ricorrenti.>

https://www.cortedicassazione.it/cassazione-resources/resources/cms/documents/Corte_Suprema_Cassazione-Relazione_2021_Primo_Presidente.pdf

A more radical operation could be carried out to make the comparison between the Italian and foreign population homogenous. In this way, the comparison between Italians and legally resident immigrants would be more homogeneous, which would benefit immigrants.²⁶

Therefore, by adopting the aforementioned measures, the overexposure of legally resident immigrants to crime is eliminated and this, in the Italian context, is a highly innovative acquisition, capable of reassuring public opinion, which is highly concerned about the criminogenic impact of immigrants.

7. Crime related to foreigners irregularly or unstably present in Italy

In addition to tourists, there are several other categories that travel for short periods of work, trade, business, shopping, visits to relatives and friends, participation in trade fairs, sports competitions and so on. The Bank of Italy, through a periodic sample survey conducted at the borders, has estimated (2016 figure) that around 50 million people enter Italy and sleep there for at least one night (in addition to those who enter and leave on the same day).

These people, even if present for short periods, are not immune from violating criminal laws. One only has to think of robberies in department stores, brawls in discos or other public establishments as a result of drunkenness, violent actions at sporting events (especially football-related), insults to public officials, political protest rallies, drug couriers and so on.

It is usually said that crime is rare among these people. But how rare is it actually? If 1 in 2,000 temporarily present foreigners were chargeable, this would still amount to 25,000 reports, and even if the recurrence were lower, the number of reports would be considerable.

For non-resident foreigners, therefore, it would be possible to know the total number of complaints (an operation that is possible for

26 Also ISTAT, commenting on the complaints that resulted in criminal proceedings in the period 2011-2014, volume *Delitti impuniti e vittime dei reati. Una lettura integrata delle fonti su crimine e giustizia* (ISTAT, Rome, 2017, p. 89) points out that those most accused are those between 18 and 49 years of age, (with higher values for those aged 35-44). Unfortunately, values for Italians and legally resident foreigners are not provided separately for the individual age groups of the defendants.

the Ministry of the Interior through the complaints archive), but the heterogeneous reference population does not allow one to proceed except with approximations.

It therefore does not seem correct to charge the narrow category of irregular immigrants (which according to the then Minister of the Interior Matteo Salvini would be around 600,000 in 2018) with all the complaints concerning non-resident foreigners. Therefore, the criminal impact of irregular immigrants must also be downgraded, although it is well known that their precarious position can expose them more frequently to deviance.

7.1 The crime rate calculated by Eurostat²⁷

In this essay I will not dwell on the overall criminal landscape found in the 28 European Union states, naturally Eurostat used the data from the national archives and, as far as Italy is concerned, the complaints from the archive of the Ministry of the Interior. Eurostat not only takes charge of data collection (the guide provides a comprehensive overview of the regular collection system), but also aligns them according to the International Classification of Criminal Offences for Statistical Purposes (Iccs), which takes into account agreed concepts, definitions and principles to improve the consistency and comparability of crime statistics. It also explains how crime rates are calculated²⁸.

The overall number of complaints decreased in several Member States, including Italy as seen before, but not in all (e.g. Germany). Complaints; compared to 100,000 foreign residents, there was a slight decrease in Italy, whereas there was an increase in Austria and France and almost a doubling in Germany). These are comparisons that can be made, albeit with due caution as we are dealing with different criminal law systems and with difficulties that have not yet been completely overcome in arriving at uniform definitions.

In Italy in 2015, the 307,781 were 580.29 per 100,000 residents, a rate, albeit slightly lower than that of Belgium, 38% lower than that of

27 Eurostat, Crime and Criminal Justice Statistics - Summary quality report on the 2015 data collection. May 2016, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Crime_statistics; https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/library-document/crime-and-immigration-evidence-large-immigrant-waves_en,

28 N.Ajzenman P. Dominguez R. Undurraga, Immigration, Crime, and Crime (Mis)Perceptions, September 2th, 2020

Switzerland, half the rate of Germany and Austria, considerably lower than that of Luxembourg and Lichtenstein but twice the rate found in France and Spain and also higher than the values found in several small Eastern European Member States.

On the whole, Italy is in a median position and within it foreigners stand out for a rate of complaints per 100,000 inhabitants that is half that of Italian citizens: a conclusion drawn from official data, validated by Eurostat but generally overlooked, although this does not obviate the problems that we shall also consider.

In Spain between 2010 and 2018, there was an increase in the number of convicts (+20.9%), from around 25,000 to 30,000. In contrast, Germany, France and Italy saw a contraction, particularly significant in France (-32.4%).

These data show that, in the face of an increase in the foreign component of the population, the level of security in EU countries as a whole has decreased slightly.

Socio-economic conditions and crime

The crime rate is higher among foreigners than among native citizens, but this statement needs a number of considerations²⁹.

First, as mentioned, a fundamental aspect of crime is that it is often determined by socio-economic hardship. This is a dimension that must be taken into account when talking about foreign crime, because foreign nationals in Europe today are significantly more exposed to poverty than natives.

In Spain and Greece, more than half of foreign residents are at risk of poverty.

The share of native and foreign citizens at risk of poverty and social exclusion in EU countries (2020) According to 'Eurostat' data, people are 'at risk of poverty or social exclusion' if they have an income below 60% of the median income (at risk of poverty), are in conditions of severe material or social deprivation (an articulated indicator that measures a person's ability to afford certain things that are not essential for survival but are necessary to lead a minimally decent life) and live in households where work intensity is very low. The data refer only to the adult popula-

29 B.Bell, F. Fasani, and S. Machin. "Crime and immigration: Evidence from large immigrant waves." *Review of Economics and Statistics* 95:4 (2013): 1278-1290

tion and, in the case of foreigners, only take into account the legally resident population (thus excluding people without a residence permit)³⁰.

The highest shares are recorded in southern European countries (Spain, Greece and Italy), while the lowest are found in some eastern European countries.

In Spain, 54% of resident foreigners are at risk of poverty and social exclusion (2020).

In addition to Spain, the disparity with native residents is also found in Sweden and France. In Sweden, almost 44% of foreigners are at risk, a figure that drops to 14% in the case of Swedish nationals. A similar situation is found in France, where the same figure stands at 44% and 15% respectively.

Foreigners and crime in Europe

As stated above, irregular foreigners, i.e. persons present in Italy but without a residence permit, commit the crimes. According to available statistical data (2008-2015) from Eurostat's 'Crime and Criminal Justice' database, a comparison of Italy, France, Germany and the United Kingdom shows that the countries have similar socio-demographic characteristics and are home to 53% of the EU population³¹.

In these four countries mentioned, the presence of foreign citizens - EU and non-EU - varies between 7 and 11%. The figures for both absolute numbers and incidence on the total population are up from 2008, by 1 per cent in France, 2 per cent in Italy and the United Kingdom, and 3 per cent in Germany, without taking into account that between 2008³² and 2015 many foreigners acquired citizenship. In France, it is estimated that about a quarter of the population is of foreign origin and a fifth in Germany. Italy, on the other hand, has seen a significant increase in the number of resident immigrants, with an increase of 1,770,000³³.

30 Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion by citizenship group (population aged 18 and over) - EU 2020 strategy[ilc_peps05]

31 Asylum applicants by type of applicant, citizenship, age and sex - annual aggregated data[migr_asyappctza]. Last update: 29-08-2022, https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=migr_asyappctza&lang=en

32 M. Katz, Charles (2008). The Connection between Illegal Immigrants and Crime. Tempe, AZ: Center for Violence Prevention and Community Safety, Arizona State University

33 B.Callaway, P. H Sant'Anna, (2020). Differences-in-differences with mu periods. Journal of Econometrics. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconom.2020.12.001>; The Role

The homicide figure in Italy also shows a steady trend below the EU average and was in 2015 below the figures for France, Germany and the United Kingdom. Compared to other countries, Italy has the lowest number of violent assaults in comparison to France, Germany and the United Kingdom, with an annual average of 111 assaults per 100,000 inhabitants, also lower than the EU average. The absolute figure drops from 65,000 aggressions in 2008 to 64,000 in 2015. Italy's 2015 figure of 57 robberies per 100,000 inhabitants is practically the same as Germany's and lower than the figures for France and the United Kingdom, and the EU average. The number of kidnappings and abductions in Italy is by far the lowest among the countries surveyed, and significantly lower than the EU average. In 2015, there were 4.7 kidnappings per 100,000 inhabitants compared to 139 kidnappings per 100,000 inhabitants in the UK.

The data on sexual violence are lower in Italy than in France, Germany and the United Kingdom with 6.5 sexual assaults per 100,000 inhabitants in 2015, and show no signs of growth in recent years. In this regard, it should be noted that more than others it suffers from a data collection problem, because much violence is not reported (often because it occurs within the home), and because national police do not always classify sexual violence under the same category.

The overall assessment of the indicators examined highlights several important aspects:

1. The general crime level in Italy is in line with and often below the European average; for some values below France, Germany and the United Kingdom.
2. From 2008 to 2018, there was no increase in value in any of the five indicators analysed; on the contrary, in most cases the trend is downward³⁴.

of Organised Crime in the Smuggling of Migrants from West Africa to the European Union. Available from www.unodc.org/unodc/en/human-trafficking/migrant-smuggling/the-role-of-organized-crime-in-the-smuggling-of-migrants-from-west-africa-to-the-european-union.htm

34 D.A. Jaeger, J Ruist, and J. Stuhler, (2018), "Shift-Share Instruments and the Impact of Immigration," National Bureau of Economic Research Working Paper 24285. Available at: <http://www.nber.org/papers/w24285>. [318]

7.2 *The presence of foreign citizens in prisons*

A possible measure of the crime rate among foreigners is their prison population. This section will analyze the evolution of the percentage of foreign prisoners over time, comparing Italy with other European Union countries. Finally, we will consider the effectiveness of this indicator in representing the actual crime rate among immigrants. According to data from the Ministry of Justice ³⁵, in 2025, Italy will have a prison population of 62,761. Of these, 19,810 would be foreign-born prisoners (31.6% of the total). According to ISTAT ³⁶, as of January 2025, 5,400,000 foreigners were resident in Italy (out of a total population of 58,934,000), approximately 9.2% of the population. This means that less than a tenth of the population represents approximately a third of the prison population.

To understand the extent of the overrepresentation of foreigners in detention facilities, we can compare Italian data with those of other European countries bordering the Mediterranean. The Council of Europe's SPACE survey is useful for this purpose³⁷. However, its latest publication concerns 2023. Therefore, compared to this year, a comparative analysis of foreign representation in European prisons will be conducted. According to SPACE I, in 2023, Spanish prison inmates accounted for 30.1% of the total; a figure very similar to the Italian one in the same year (31.5%). The percentage shown by France (25.1%) is not excessively lower, and that of Greece (56.8%) is much higher. With the exception of Greece, the Italian experience does not differ much from the situation in other countries. It should also be added that, in Italy, the percentage of foreigners in prison has decreased over the years. According to data from the SPACE I survey, it was 34.1% in 2018 and has steadily decreased over the following five years. To provide a dynamic representation of the phenomenon in Italy, the Antigone association notes in its end-2024 report³⁸ that since 2007, the

35 4 Ministry of Justice. (2025). Statistics – Inmates present by crime and nationality (data as of May 31, 2025). Department of Penitentiary Administration.

https://www.giustizia.it/giustizia/en/mg_1_14_1.page?contentId=SST1456994

36 ISTAT. (2025). Annual Report 2025 – The Situation of the Country. Press Notes (Updated Version). National Institute of Statistics. https://www.ISTAT.it/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/PILLOLE-PER-LA-STAMPA_RAPPORTO-ANNUALE-2025_rev.pdf

37 Council of Europe (2023), "SPACE I – Survey on Prison Populations", University of Lausanne – Council of Europe, <https://wp.unil.ch/space/space-i/>

38 7 Antigone Association (2024), "End of year report on prison conditions in Italy", December 2024

percentage of foreigners in prison has decreased by 5.6%, reaching 31.9% by December 2024. It should also be noted that, despite this reduction, in that period, the foreign population in Italy has increased from 3 million in 2007 to 5 million in 2023.

7.3 Distorting factors: pre-trial detention and alternative measures to detention

At this point, one might be tempted to conclude that an over-representation of foreigners among prisoners implies a higher crime rate among this group. However, using prison data as an estimator of the crime rate presents some critical issues that could lead to an overestimation of foreigners' propensity to commit crimes.

A first aspect to consider is that prison population data includes a portion of inmates awaiting trial for whom no crime has been proven. If the share of inmates not subject to a final sentence were the same for Italians and foreigners, crime rate estimates would not be misleading. If, however, it were different, the estimates would be distorted. Council of Europe data show that, in 2023³⁹, 30.1% of foreign-born inmates were held in pretrial detention, compared to 26.5% of Italian inmates. Looking at the data available for the previous five years, it is clear that this gap is still present, despite having narrowed significantly. The 2023 data for France are very similar to those for Italy, with 31.6% of foreign inmates in pretrial detention compared to 25.2% for French inmates. The gap shown by Spain is even more marked: 28.1% for foreigners and only 11.3% for native-born inmates. Leaving aside considerations regarding the causes of this evidence, it can be stated that the number of foreigners detained before trial is significantly higher than the share of native-born citizens. Using prison data as a crime index would ignore the latter aspect and overestimate the prevalence of crime among foreign-born citizens. A further source of distortion in the estimates concerns the possibility of accessing alternatives to prison for those convicted. Again, if the probability of obtaining an alternative to prison were the same for both groups, the estimate would not be misleading. According to data from the Ministry of Justice⁴⁰, however, in May

39 Although the Ministry of Justice has published data updated to 2025, it is more convenient to use the 2023 Council of Europe data, since it is comparable with that of other European countries.

40 Ministry of Justice – Department of Juvenile and Community Justice, Adults in External Penal Areas – Provisional Data as of May 31, 2025, Rome, Ministry of Justi-

2025, only 20.6% of those in custody at the External Penal Enforcement Offices were foreigners (29,591 out of 143,326), despite the fact that in December 2024, they represented ⁴¹45.5% of inmates sentenced to less than one year in prison (625 out of 1,373), a requirement for obtaining this type of sentence. This shows a greater likelihood of Italians accessing alternative measures than foreigners. Looking only at prison data, a greater share of Italian criminals would be missing compared to the share of foreigners. This would again have the effect of overestimating the crime rate among foreigners. In light of what has been said so far, it can be concluded that the incidence of foreigners in prison is a misleading indicator of an immigrant's likelihood of committing crimes. An indicator that would avoid the two problems associated with prison data would be the one related to convictions. This would exclude from the sample those who are detained but still awaiting trial, and include all those who are convicted but not currently in prison because they are beneficiaries of alternative measures. This will be the focus of the next section.

We concluded that the incidence of foreigners in prisons was a misleading indicator of this group's crime rate. We then observed that data on reports would address the critical issues presented by prison data. In this chapter, we will therefore study conviction data, focusing on the Italian context, with the aim of constructing a differential crime rate between Italians and foreigners. If this were possible, it would be possible to compare the exposure to crime of the two groups and, ultimately, investigate the origins of any discrepancies.

A primary source of this overrepresentation of foreigners among reports may be due to their irregular status. In the Italian legal context, the status of legal immigrant is governed by the Consolidated Law on Immigration (Legislative Decree No. 286 of 25 July 1998). Pursuant to Article 5, paragraph 1, a legal immigrant is a third-country national who holds a valid residence permit, issued by the competent authorities, for stays exceeding ninety days. Legal residence requires compliance with the conditions estab-

ce, 2025, available at: https://www.giustizia.it/cmsresources/cms/documents/Adulti_in_area_penale_externa_31.5.2025_G.pdf (accessed June 15, 2025)

41 Ministry of Justice – Department of Penitentiary Administration, *Inmates Present by Length of Sentence – Data Updated as of December 31, 2024*, Rome, Ministry of Justice, 2024, available at: https://www.giustizia.it/giustizia/it/mg_1_14_1.page?contentId=SST1438122 (accessed July 14, 2025).

lished by law, such as the absence of relevant criminal convictions, renewal of the permit within the established deadlines, and compliance with any residence requirements. Otherwise, the foreigner is considered illegal and may be subject to administrative measures, including expulsion or restrictions on access to certain rights. Holders of residence permits that are no longer valid, people who came to Italy without a visa (or more often with a tourist visa) and overstayed their stay, asylum seekers who were denied entry and failed to comply with an order to leave Italy, and people who arrived in Italy without authorization and remained in Italy even though they had been ordered to expel are considered irregular. Their number fluctuates annually between 400,000 and 600,000 units, constituting approximately 10 % of the immigrant population. The possibility of greater exposure of irregular foreigners to crime is based on the “economic theory of crime” formulated by Gary Becker (1968)⁴². According to this approach, each individual rationally chooses whether to commit a crime, comparing expected benefits and costs. The latter include the probability of being caught and punished (which has a deterrent effect on crime), but also the opportunity cost of the illegal activity, which represents everything an individual must forgo by choosing to commit crime—that is, the benefits they would gain by engaging in remunerative legal activities. Extending this theoretical framework to the specific case of undocumented immigrants would explain why they are more likely to commit crimes. Indeed, precisely because of their irregular status, they lack access to the formal labor market. Therefore, by deciding not to engage in criminal activity, they could only do so through casual or undeclared work. Therefore, their expected legal income, which is the opportunity cost of committing crime, is very low, or at least lower than that of a legal immigrant. Compared to the latter, they also have less access to education and training, which in the long run would increase their expected income by increasing the cost of committing crime. Finally, regarding the possibility of being caught and punished, the other component of the cost of committing crime may lose its deterrent effect for an irregular immigrant. Indeed, if they had a high probability of being expelled and repatriated regardless of the crime, the additional risk of facing punishment would be much lower. According to economic theory, therefore, irregular immigrants would be more likely to engage in criminal

42 G. S. Becker, (1968). Crime and Punishment: An Economic Approach. *Journal of Political Economy*, 76(2), 169–217.

activity. Some empirical studies, including those by Paolo Pinotti⁴³, isolate the causal effects of foreigners' irregular status, showing that, once regularized, they have lower recidivism rates. This section focuses on the Italian context and, in particular, on the proportion of reported foreigners who are irregular. An initial contribution in this regard comes from the study conducted by the IDOS Study and Research Center with the support of the Redattore Sociale news agency in 2009. It analyzed data from ISTAT (the Italian National Institute of Statistics) regarding reports that resulted in legal action in 2005. As previously noted, ISTAT processes data produced by the Ministry of Justice, which can be disaggregated between foreigners and Italians, but does not allow for the distinction between illegal immigrants. IDOS therefore integrated the ISTAT data with data produced by the Ministry of the Interior, based on the SDI archive, regarding the percentage distribution of reports between foreigners with a residence permit and other foreigners, considering this data applicable to the ISTAT data. These data revealed that of the 550,590 reports with a known perpetrator in 2005, 130,458 involved foreigners, but only 28.9% (37,709 reports) involved foreigners with a valid residence permit. Seven out of every ten reports attributed to foreigners were perpetrators with an irregular residence permit or transient status. In some criminal offenses, such as theft, the incidence of undocumented foreigners exceeds 80% of the reports attributed to foreigners. The 2011 study "Report on Crime and Security in Italy 2010" by Barbagli M. and Colombo A. reaches the same conclusions, adding a temporal dimension to the study by analyzing Ministry of the Interior data regarding reports by known perpetrators from 1988 to 2009. The incidence of irregular immigrants in reports against foreigners was measured, as in the previous study, breaking down the data by type of crime. It is noted that the percentage of irregular immigrants among those reported decreased slightly between 1989 and 2009, from an average of 80% to approximately 70%. For some specific crimes, such as theft, it remained consistently higher than average: in 2009, for example, irregular immigrants accounted for 78% of foreigners reported for this type of crime. This is consistent with the IDOS study. An additional effort was made to compare the crime rate of Italians and foreigners, subsequently isolating

43 P. Pinotti, (2017). Clicking on Heaven's Door: Immigration and Crime in Italy. *American Economic Journal: Economic Policy*, 9(1), 1–38. <https://doi.org/10.1257/pol.20150297>

the legal component. The crime rate is calculated by dividing the number of crimes committed by a group by its size. While there are no problems calculating the denominator for Italians, this is true for the foreign component. As we have seen, approximately 70% of the crimes committed by this group are attributable to individuals who do not possess a residence permit. Therefore, both foreigners with a residence permit and illegal immigrants and those in transit should be included. Otherwise, the crime rate would tend to be overestimated. ISTAT makes the "archive of foreign residents" available. However, using this data presents several problems. First, it does not include some foreigners with a residence permit, due to the lengthy process of registering in the municipal registry (over several years, several hundred thousand individuals were involved). Then there are foreign citizens who enter Italy legally with short-term visas (which do not require a residence permit) or even visa-free, depending on international agreements. Added to these are those who, despite having entered legally, overstay their welcome, and those who enter illegally, the extent of which remains difficult to estimate. An estimate of the size of these flows emerges from a sample survey by the Bank of Italy, which shows that over 50 million people enter Italy from abroad each year.

To obtain reliable crime rates, ISTAT data must be supplemented with an estimate of the number of foreigners actually present in Italy, given their greater incidence of crime. This is the direction taken by IDOS (2009) research, already mentioned in this thesis, which attempted to estimate a more realistic crime rate among foreigners by supplementing official data with an estimate of their actual presence. The results show a rate of 0.75% for Italians, while for foreigners it is 1.41% if referred to residents only, and 1.24% if calculated on the total foreign population according to IDOS estimates. As can be seen, the gap between the two groups exists, but it is not as marked as comparisons based solely on the resident population would suggest. This section has shown how part of the overrepresentation of foreigners in crime reports is due to the irregular component, which accounts for approximately 70% of all reports against foreigners. Taking into account the proportion of those without residence permits, the estimated crime rate among foreigners is 1.24%, which is still significantly higher than the Italian rate (0.75%). The following discussion will explore the other variables that explain this overrepresentation.

7.4 Violations of the TUI

When comparing crime rates among Italians and foreigners, it is important to consider the points made by Pittau and Iafrate (2018), who highlight that, to make the two groups comparable, it is necessary to separate from the total crimes attributed to foreigners those related to violations of the Consolidated Law on Immigration (Legislative Decree 286/1998). These include, for example, illegal entry into the national territory, overstaying a visa or residence permit, failure to comply with an expulsion order, and other similar crimes. These are all crimes that Italian citizens could not commit. Failure to consider this aspect would overestimate the difference in crime rates between the two groups. According to ISTAT data, in 2012 these crimes constituted 17.7% of the total crimes attributed to foreigners. The same authors observe that, if the percentage of reports referring to legal residents were still the same as that recorded in 2005 (therefore excluding illegal immigrants), and the percentage calculated by ISTAT for 2009 were adopted for violations of the Consolidated Law on Immigration, the crime rate of legally resident foreigners would be similar to that of Italians.

7.5 Summary of results

Initial data showed that 32% of reports with a known perpetrator involved foreign nationals, compared to a population prevalence of approximately 9%. Further analysis revealed that over 70% of these reports involved individuals who, for various reasons, lacked a valid residence permit. The higher concentration of foreigners in the age groups most exposed to crime (18-44) was then taken into account. A comparison of rates by age was then conducted, which isolated the issue of the different distribution between the two groups. This significantly reduced the observed gap in crime rates. A fair comparison, truly isolating the propensity for criminal behavior between the two groups, should be made by considering only crimes committed by legally resident foreigners, comparing crime rates by different age groups, without considering crimes committed by foreigners in violation of the TUI. This would significantly reduce the gap between the two groups.

The socioeconomic and family factors that often characterize the condition of immigrants should also be considered. This would allow for a complete explanation of the phenomenon, but it goes beyond the objectives of this paper.

Conclusions

The texts by the sociologists Barbagli and Solivetti (the scholars cited at the beginning), despite the criticisms levelled at them here concerning the determination of the crime rate of regularly resident immigrants, are appreciable for several reasons: the inclusion of the Italian case in the international context, the commentary on theories of deviance, the accurate presentation of the sources used and the historical trend of the data, the reflections on the conditions that favour deviance, the shortcomings of migration policy, the analysis of the most serious or widespread crimes and the reference to criminal organisations. However, it is reiterated, the high crime rate they attribute to legally resident immigrants is not convincing, without adequately taking into account the factors that can reduce the attributions.

The high incidence of complaints for violations of the rules of the Consolidated Immigration Act represents a fundamental point to be investigated, not only to know exactly their current quantitative dimension, but also to examine individual violations. In addition to the twenty or so cases previously taken into account by the SDI archive in the registration of complaints, several other cases have been added following the ‘security decree’ (Decree-Law No. 113/2018 conv. in Law No. 132/2018) and the second security decree (Decree-Law No. 53/2019 conv. in Law No. 77/2019⁴⁴, nonché delle recenti modifiche introdotte dal Decreto Legge 21 ottobre 2020, n. 130 conv. in Legge n.173/2020 e dalla Legge n.50/2023⁴⁵).

In this regard, it should be noted that, just as criminal regulations are necessary, it is equally advisable to avoid that regulations on flows (which are the responsibility of demographic and employment policy) increasingly fall into the criminal sphere. There seems to be good reason to believe that the rigidity with which permits for humanitarian reasons were abolished increased the number of irregular presences, with wide repercussions also

44 P. Iafrate, 2020, in “Judicium”, “Legge n. 77/21019 o di conversione del cd. “decreto legge Salvini n.53/2019”: anche gli interventi in materia di ordine e sicurezza pubblica sono soggetti a limiti”; dicembre 2020, ISSN 2533-0632, <http://www.judicium.it/legge-n-7721019-conversione-del-cd-decreto-legge-salvini-n-532019->

45 Law no. 50 of 5 May 2023, Conversion into law, with amendments, of Decree-Law no. 20 of 10 March 2023, containing urgent provisions on the subject of legal entry flows of foreign workers and the prevention and fight against irregular immigration. <https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2023-05-05;50>

on the phenomenon of crime, so that the changes subsequently made by Law No. 173/2020⁴⁶ may have a positive effect.

The conclusions reached in this article, through an interpretative line that has been conducted for years with Franco Pittau within the Idos Study and Research Centre, are not due to so-called 'goodism' but rather to an accurate assessment of the data considered in their entirety. The result arrived at must be considered a stimulus for further comparisons. The aim is to deactivate a dangerous divide between Italians and immigrants, preventing them from being considered 'non-integratable' due to their assumed structural predisposition to delinquency.

It is emphasised, once again, that by downgrading the crime rate of legally resident immigrants, the intention was not to state that their deviance is a matter of little importance, but only to question the very high level attributed to them.

According to the methodological approach proposed here, Italians and legal immigrants are at approximately the same level as regards criminality and, therefore, the concern of whether one group is more deviant than the other becomes less suffocating. It seems more relevant to focus more on prevention, integration, intercultural dialogue, and the involvement of immigrant associations to make the law-abiding path more attractive, bearing in mind that deviance is increased in environments that are hostile to immigrants and their integration.

Together with the Idos researchers who have opened this interpretative hypothesis, it is hoped to have demonstrated, on the basis of the data, the path taken by foreign citizens who have settled in Italy to be more

46 P Iafrate (2022). La legge 18 dicembre 2020, n.173 tra innovazioni e criticità. JUDICIUM, p. 1-19, ISSN: 2533-0632, Audizioni informali, della I COMMISSIONE (AFFARI COSTITUZIONALI, DELLA PRESIDENZA DEL CONSIGLIO E INTERNI) della Camera dei deputati in videoconferenza (con l'invio di memoria). Osservazioni sul disegno di legge "Disposizioni urgenti in materia di immigrazione e sicurezza" A.C. 2727, di conversione del decreto legge del 21 ottobre 2020 n.130, recante "Disposizioni urgenti in materia di immigrazione, protezione internazionale e complementare, modifiche agli articoli 131 -bis , 391 -bis , 391 -ter e 588 del codice penale, nonché misure in materia di divieto di accesso agli esercizi pubblici ed ai locali di pubblico trattenimento, di contrasto all'utilizzo distorto del web e di disciplina del Garante nazionale dei diritti delle persone private della libertà personale", https://www.camera.it/application/xmanager/projects/leg18/attachments/upload_file_doc_acquisiti/pdfs/000/004/153/Memoria_Paolo_Iafrate_2.11.2020_.pdf, 3, Iafrate P (2022). La legge 18 dicembre 2020, n.173 tra innovazioni e criticità. JUDICIUM, p. 1-19, ISSN: 2533-0632

satisfactory (or less worrying) than that taken by Italians. This is of great support to those who strive for a society more open to integration and inclusion.

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